

Title: AI Assistants: Empowering Robots For Meaningful Human Interactions

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Named a "Cool Vendor" in the "Cool Vendors in Unified Communication, 2017" report by Gartner, Inc.

INTRODUCTION:

Robots present an exciting opportunity for meaningful human interactions in the near future. Combining themes in artificial intelligence, context aware predictive computing, IoT, the augmented human, and intelligent assistants this talk is an exploration into how robots can become an integral part of meaningful human interactions and what the impact will be on business and society.

AIM:

To define meaningful human interactions, identify component functions and business use cases for robots to deliver on their technological promise.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Multiple robotic platforms are examined to determine their suitability for the core requirements for meaningful human interactions. Interviews and discussions with manufacturer representatives and software creators form the basis for the discussion.

RESULTS:

Robotic hardware and systems software provides the basis and limitation for meaningful human interactions. Appropriate use case definition and limitation is critical to successful introduction of robots into complex environments. Software applications that can adapt with reinforcement learning or genetic algorithms are highly likely to provide significant value in this space.

CONCLUSIONS:

Robotic platforms that have access to and augment artificial intelligence powered applications that provide for meaningful human interactions will share in the credit for that value creation and delivery.

KEYWORDS:

Robot Autonomy, Decision Making, Domestic Robots, Intelligence Control Systems, Human Centered Robots, Speech Recognition, YOLO (Real-time computer vision and image classification) Artificial Intelligence, Reinforcement Learning, Genetic Algorithms, Machine Learning, Data Science, Internet of Things, IoT, Context Aware Predictive Computing, Skejul

BIOGRAPHY:

Matthew Lamons is the founder of Skejul. Drawing upon a background in Behavioral Science and a magnetic enthusiasm for Applied Artificial Intelligence, Matthew looks to empower people with exciting new AI technologies and the data we create to simplify the future. Matthew has been honored as an invited speaker on A.I. Topics at conferences and to contribute to global publications. You can follow him on twitter: @mlamons1 to get daily news on Data Science and A.I. He's an incurable Sci-Fi fan and lives in the mid-west (U.S.A.) with his wife Kristine, of 29 years.